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**Cultural identity as a factor in the competitiveness of gastronomic projects in
a multinational environment**

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Abstract. In today's globalized society, gastronomy ceases to be just a sphere of consumption and gains importance as a cultural code, a means of communication, and a tool for representing identity. In a multinational environment, authentic gastronomic practices face the challenges of standardization, commercialization, and the need for cultural adaptation. In this context, cultural identity increases as a factor in preserving traditions and forming a unique market offer that can ensure the competitiveness of a gastronomic project at the local and international levels. The **article aims** to substantiate the role of cultural identity as a strategic resource for the competitiveness of gastronomic projects in a multicultural environment by analyzing its content, methods of representation, and perception by consumers, as well as studying practical models of its effective use in branding and positioning. **Methods.** The study used an interdisciplinary approach that combines methods of cultural analysis, content analysis, comparative analysis of brands of gastronomic projects, and generalization of scientific sources on gastronomic marketing and socio-cultural anthropology. **Results.** As a result of the study, it was found that cultural identity in

the field of gastronomy performs not only a symbolic, but also an economic function: it contributes to the formation of a differentiated offer, the creation of emotional attachment of consumers to the brand, and increases its trust. A multicultural environment has proven to influence the reception of authentic gastronomic concepts, forming a demand for a combination of the local and the universal. Based on the analysis of the practices of regional and global projects, effective models of integrating cultural identity into brand communication strategies and the organization of gastronomic space have been identified. **Conclusions.** The study's results confirm that cultural identity acts as a means of preserving gastronomic heritage and an effective branding tool in a multicultural environment. Adapting traditional elements to the expectations of different target audiences strengthens gastronomic projects' competitiveness and contributes to the development of gastronomic tourism. At the same time, further scientific research should focus on developing applied models of communication of authentic cultural meanings in the globalized consumer space.

Keywords: globalization, transmission of values, authenticity, cooking traditions, consumption methods.

Культурна ідентичність як чинник конкурентоспроможності гастрономічних проєктів у багатонаціональному середовищі

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Анотація. У сучасному глобалізованому суспільстві гастрономія перестає бути лише сферою споживання і набуває значення як культурний код, засіб комунікації та інструмент репрезентації ідентичності. У багатонаціональному середовищі автентичні гастрономічні практики

зіштовхуються з викликами стандартизації, комерціалізації та потреби культурної адаптації. Саме в цьому контексті зростає значення культурної ідентичності як чинника не лише збереження традицій, але й формування унікальної ринкової пропозиції, що здатна забезпечити конкурентоспроможність гастрономічного проєкту на локальному та міжнародному рівнях. **Метою** статті є обґрунтування ролі культурної ідентичності як стратегічного ресурсу конкурентоспроможності гастрономічних проєктів у мультикультурному середовищі шляхом аналізу її змісту, способів репрезентації та сприйняття з боку споживачів, а також вивчення практичних моделей її ефективного використання у брендуванні та позиціонуванні. **Методи.** У дослідженні використано міждисциплінарний підхід, який поєднує методи культурологічного аналізу, контент-аналізу, порівняльного аналізу брендів гастрономічних проєктів, а також узагальнення наукових джерел з гастрономічного маркетингу та соціокультурної антропології. **Результати.** З'ясовано, що культурна ідентичність у сфері гастрономії виконує не лише символічну, а й економічну функцію: вона сприяє формуванню диференційованої пропозиції, створенню емоційної прив'язаності споживачів до бренду та підвищенню його довіри. Доведено, що мультикультурне середовище впливає на рецепцію автентичних гастрономічних концепцій, формуючи запит на поєднання локального й універсального. На основі аналізу практик локальних і глобальних проєктів виділено ефективні моделі інтеграції культурної ідентичності у комунікаційні стратегії бренду та організацію гастрономічного простору. **Висновки.** Результати дослідження підтверджують, що культурна ідентичність виступає не лише як засіб збереження гастрономічної спадщини, а й як ефективний інструмент брендування у багатокультурному середовищі. Адаптація традиційних елементів до очікувань різних цільових аудиторій дозволяє посилити конкурентоспроможність гастрономічних проєктів та сприяє

розвитку гастрономічного туризму. Водночас подальші наукові пошуки мають бути зосереджені на розробці прикладних моделей комунікації автентичних культурних смислів у глобалізованому споживчому просторі.

Ключові слова: глобалізація, трансляція цінностей, автентичність, традиції приготування, способи споживання.

Problem statement. In the current conditions of globalization and growing cultural interaction between peoples, the issue of preserving and promoting cultural identity as an element of social and economic capital is becoming increasingly relevant. This is especially true for gastronomic projects, which are a tool for satisfying basic needs and a powerful means of communication, broadcasting values, and promoting the uniqueness of national cultures. However, in a multinational environment, where consumers have access to a wide range of culinary traditions, the problem of competitiveness of such projects arises: how to stand out against the background of a globalized offer, remaining authentic and at the same time attractive to a diverse audience. The lack of a holistic scientific analysis of cultural identity's role in forming sustainable competitive advantages in the field of gastronomic business necessitates a comprehensive study of this issue. The question arises of how cultural identity can be transformed from an element of local tradition into a strategic resource that ensures the successful integration of a gastronomic project into a multicultural environment.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In modern scientific discourse, gastronomic projects are increasingly considered an essential element of socio-cultural identity and a tool for increasing the tourist attractiveness of territories. The studies of A. Aguirregoitia, S. Fernández [1] emphasize gastronomy as a resource for the tourist attractiveness of regions, particularly on the example of the province of Alicante, where local culinary traditions are used to form a unique image of the destination. A similar role of gastronomy as a factor in territorial

branding is confirmed by the works of J. Espinosa et al. [2], who analyze the Cuban experience of identifying culture through gastronomic heritage, emphasizing the importance of authenticity for forming an emotional connection with the tourist.

The study of W. Chan et al. [3] focuses on the behavioral motives of consumers of gastronomic services, particularly the desire for experience, uniqueness, and departure from standardized rituals, which actualizes the role of innovations in designing gastronomic projects while preserving local identity. The analysis of the international competitiveness of the food industry, conducted by M. Hamulczuk and K. Pawlak [4], outlines the macroeconomic and institutional factors that influence the success of the industry, while emphasizing the importance of intangible resources, in particular reputational capital, which can be formed based on cultural features.

The work of L. Correa García [5] is devoted to the analysis of factors of competitiveness of restaurants in the Mexican city of Zacatecas, where the critical importance of local culture as the basis of gastronomic authenticity and a strategic asset in the conditions of tourist competition is emphasized. The study of L. Potemkin et al. [6] studied the influence of the external environment on the development of the restaurant industry of the Odessa region, in particular through the prism of gastronomic tourism, which allows for outlining the regional features of positioning projects with a national cultural component. S. Krasovsky [7] treats gastronomic tourism as a trend of modern culture, reflecting deep transformations of social practices and the need for authentic experience. At the same time, V. Glushko [8] systematizes gastronomic tourism as an independent phenomenon within the tourism industry, identifying classification features, which include cultural markers. The work of G. Sarkissian [9] reveals the mechanisms for stimulating gastronomic tourism in the regional dimension, emphasizing the role of organizational and managerial approaches to popularizing local cuisine.

The key approach to studying the role of cultural identity is that of P. Gerchanivska [10], who treats identity as a resource of social development capable of mobilizing both social capital and economic potential. Her view allows us to consider the gastronomic sphere not only in a financial or touristic sense but primarily in a cultural sense - as a medium for transmitting and representing shared values.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Existing research confirms the importance of gastronomy as a resource for tourism and economic development, as evidenced by analytical research on regional branding, image formation of territories, and the introduction of local culinary traditions into the tourism infrastructure. However, several aspects have not yet received sufficient theoretical and applied understanding. In particular, modern scientific literature does not consider the mechanisms of integrating elements of cultural identity into the structure of commercial gastronomic projects in the context of intercultural communication. Existing approaches focus mainly on a single-vector presentation of traditional cuisine as an exotic component for an external consumer, which often does not consider the audience's heterogeneity and the need for flexible adaptation of cultural codes.

Also, the question of how a multicultural environment influences consumer expectations and, therefore, strategic decisions in the brand management of restaurant concepts remains insufficiently researched. The mechanisms of transformation of cultural content into elements of a value proposition relevant to globalized markets remain fragmentarily covered in the professional literature. At the same time, the lack of systemic models that would describe the relationship between the local content of a gastronomic offer and the requirements of a multicultural audience does not allow for a practical assessment of the potential of cross-cultural authenticity as a marketing resource. This creates a conceptual gap, which this article is intended to fill partially. It focuses on analyzing the interaction

of cultural identity, consumer expectations, and branding strategies of gastronomic projects in a globalized environment.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (task statement). The purpose of the article is to analyze the role of cultural identity as a factor in the formation of the competitiveness of gastronomic projects in a multinational environment, to identify mechanisms for its effective integration into the development strategy of such projects, and to outline the conditions under which it turns into a sustainable competitive advantage.

The objectives of the article:

- to reveal the essence of the concept of cultural identity and its significance in the field of gastronomy;
- to investigate the influence of a multicultural environment on the perception of authentic gastronomic projects by consumers;
- to analyze the practices of cultural identity as an element of branding and differentiation of gastronomic products and services.

Presentation of the primary material of the study. Cultural identity is a multifaceted phenomenon formed by historical, ethnic, religious, linguistic, and other factors. In the scientific literature, cultural identity is considered a system of symbols, meanings, and practices through which individuals identify themselves with a particular group. As noted by V. Glushko, according to S. Hall's approaches, cultural identity is not a stable or closed structure; it is dynamic, changing under the influence of external and internal factors, in particular as a result of globalization processes and intercultural communication [8, p. 167]. This concept is key for analyzing the social construction of communities, as it determines how to preserve and transmit traditions, norms of behavior, values, and forms of expression of cultural difference. In the field of gastronomy, cultural identity acquires special importance, acting as one of the most stable and at the same time the most expressive markers of national and ethnic belonging. Food performs not only a biological

function but also carries symbolic meaning, enshrined in the recipe, cooking traditions, and consumption methods. Thus, gastronomic culture allows us to represent and at the same time reproduce the specifics of ethno-national traditions. In the commercialization of gastronomy, particularly in the restaurant business, local culinary traditions are actively used as the basis for creating an authentic image of the establishment, forming an emotional connection with the consumer, and differentiation in the market [9, p. 315].

Cultural identity in the gastronomic context can manifest itself at several levels: at the product level (use of local ingredients, traditional recipes), at the service level (culturally determined service rituals, language policy of the staff), as well as at the spatial level (architectural design, musical accompaniment, ethnic symbols in the interior). Thus, gastronomic projects that incorporate elements of cultural identity into their concept form a special type of consumer experience. That is why national cuisine, local recipes, regional culinary techniques, dish decoration, architecture of the gastronomic space, service, and ritual of eating can be understood as carriers of cultural identity and at the same time as factors of competitiveness. In this context, not only does the authentic content of the gastronomic offer become significant, but it also allows the consumer to adapt it to the expectations without losing cultural value. This poses a dual challenge for contemporary projects: on the one hand, to preserve uniqueness as a key characteristic of their identity, and on the other, to create an inclusive space capable of engaging representatives of different cultures in dialogue through gastronomic practices [10].

In an international context, a gastronomic product begins to perform the function of a “cultural translator”, through which the consumer becomes acquainted with other traditions, symbols, and meanings. At the same time, such a reception is not neutral or universal – it always depends on the competence of the consumer, his ability to interpret authenticity not as an exotic element or tourist attraction, but as a manifestation of a holistic cultural system. In this aspect, knowledge of the product's

origin, previous experience of travel or communication with its representatives, and the level of openness to the “other” within one’s own identity play an important role.

Studies conducted in culinary anthropology and marketing show that in multicultural societies, authentic gastronomic projects are often perceived through the prism of stereotypes, exoticization, or reduction. For example, national cuisine can be reduced to a few popularized dishes that only partially reflect its real structure. At the same time, due to commercialization, traditional recipes are adapted to the taste preferences of the majority, which threatens authenticity as a value. This phenomenon has been called “culinary compromise” or “cultural hybridization”, when the focus is not on preserving tradition, but on adapting it to the dominant gastronomic paradigm [11].

However, a multicultural environment also creates opportunities for the growth of the popularity of gastronomy as a marker of a unique experience. In globalized consumption, the demand for “ethnic food” or “world cuisine” that represents other cultures is growing. In this case, authenticity becomes a competitive advantage that allows the project to stand out among standardized formats [12]. However, it should be not only declarative, but also experiential: the consumer expects not just a national dish, but complete immersion in the cultural context, through the interior, music, service, and the history of the origin of dishes.

Thus, the perception of a gastronomic project in a multicultural environment becomes a complex phenomenon in which the culinary offer is combined with narratives, symbols, and emotional resonance. That is why it is advisable to systematically understand the key factors that determine the nature of the perception of authenticity in conditions of cultural diversity, considering the degree of adaptability, narrative potential, typology of the environment, and the level of intercultural competence of the consumer [13]. To illustrate and generalize the relationships between these factors, it is proposed to consider various models of

interaction of gastronomic projects with a multicultural environment, which reveal the potential of cultural identity as a tool for strategic positioning (table 1).

In the context of growing competition among gastronomic projects, particularly in multicultural urban centers and tourist regions, there is a growing need to implement practical models that integrate an authentic cultural component into business strategies to attract a wider audience, build consumer loyalty, and ensure economic sustainability. One of the most effective models is the authentic branding strategy, which involves creating a gastronomic project brand around culturally marked symbols – traditional recipes, local design elements, historical narratives, and regional gastronomic heritage. In such a model, it is essential to use “cultural markers” and to form a consistent communicative message representing the values of the community of origin. This approach is efficient in cases where the target audience has a heightened interest in cultural tourism or the experience of “real” gastronomic immersion [14, p. 307].

Table 1

Interaction of authentic gastronomic projects and multicultural environment

Analytical aspect	Content	Examples	Analytical conclusions / potential
Type of perception of authenticity	Authenticity as exoticism / as cultural depth	Japanese cuisine as "fashionable" - Sushi / traditional kaiseki	Superficial perception reduces cultural value, while deep perception forms a lasting interest
Consumer cultural competence	High / medium / low	Tourist with experience in the country of origin / average consumer	The ability to interpret the authentic context depends on the level of competence
Level of adaptation of the project to the environment	Complete authenticity/ partial adaptation/hybridization	Ethnic restaurant without recipe changes/adaptation of spices to local taste	Partial adaptation can promote acceptance, but risks devaluing authenticity
Type of multicultural space	Cosmopolitan environment/diaspora / tourism / academic environment	New York (interculturality), Lviv (tourism), Paris (diasporas)	The type of environment influences expectations and forms of communication with the gastroproject

Form of engagement with culture through food	Passive consumption / cultural participation / gastronomic education	Network fast food with a national brand / culinary master classes	The deeper the engagement, the stronger the intercultural empathy is formed
Cultural narrative management	Retelling traditions/brand legend / ideology of sustainable heritage	Stories about the origin of dishes, emphasis on local products	The presence of a narrative strengthens the emotional connection and supports cultural identity
Economic feasibility of authenticity	High demand - high margin / low demand - the need for adaptation	Demand for regional Italian cuisine/niche oriental cuisines	Authenticity can be both a source of profit and require investment in marketing

Source: author's development

Another effective model is the intercultural interpretation of traditional cuisine, which provides a balance between preserving identity and adapting to a multicultural context [15, p. 130]. In this case, gastronomic projects modify recipes, cooking technologies, or serving dishes without significantly losing authentic content. This approach allows for higher accessibility and acceptability for consumers who are not always ready for radically different gastronomic practices. The success of this model depends on the ability to preserve the symbolic value of cultural tradition in an updated format.

The third practical model is creating a gastronomic space as a platform for intercultural dialogue [16, p. 78]. Within this paradigm, restaurants, cafes, or gastrobars function as food establishments and cultural centers where traditions, experiences, and stories intersect. The format of events, such as culinary master classes, tastings with commentary, themed evenings, or presentations, increases interpersonal interaction and creates conditions for forming an emotional connection with the consumer. In this way, the gastronomic product acquires the status of a communicative tool between cultures.

Also noteworthy is the partnership model with local communities and carriers of traditional culinary culture. This approach allows for integrating living knowledge and practices into modern commercial activities, creating a product that is not just a stylization of tradition but also embodies its real evolution. Cooperation with local producers, the use of regional raw materials, and the involvement of local chefs who are carriers of culinary tradition increase the credibility of the gastronomic experience and, at the same time, contribute to the sustainable development of regional cultural and economic ecosystems [17].

Finally, another promising strategy is integrating digital tools to promote cultural identity [18]. In this context, digital content creation becomes important - video stories about dishes, interactive menus with an explanation of the cultural origin of ingredients, virtual tours of gastronomic regions, blogs, podcasts, etc. Such tools allow you to scale access to authentic experiences, reach new audiences, and increase cultural awareness of consumers in the global digital environment.

Thus, practical models for increasing the competitiveness of gastronomic projects based on cultural identity are multidimensional and require a comprehensive approach. They are not reduced to superficial ethnic stylization but involve the holistic integration of the artistic component into all levels of strategic planning, marketing, product design, and interaction with the consumer [19]. In the future, such models will contribute to economic efficiency, deepen intercultural understanding, and preserve cultural diversity in the global world.

Conclusions. The study made it possible to comprehensively analyze the phenomenon of cultural identity in the context of the development of gastronomic projects in a multinational environment and to outline its role as a factor in the formation of competitiveness in the conditions of a globalized economy. The essence of cultural identity as a multilevel construct is revealed, including collective belonging, historical continuity, symbolic meanings, and social practices represented through gastronomic activity. In gastronomy, cultural identity is

expressed in ingredients, recipes, or cooking methods and in narratives, spatial design, communication styles, and value systems transmitted to the consumer. It is through gastronomic practices that cultural memory is materialized, transforming food into a medium of socio-cultural dialogue.

The specifics of the perception of authentic gastronomic projects in a multicultural environment are analyzed. It is established that such interaction is characterized by ambivalence: on the one hand, there is a growing interest in authenticity as a symbol of uniqueness and exoticism; on the other hand, consumer expectations are often formed under the influence of globalized taste norms and standardized service models. This necessitates adapting the gastronomic offer to the intercultural context without losing its core identity. Thus, the success of a gastronomic project depends on its ability to simultaneously maintain cultural authenticity and be open to interpretation, dialogue, and flexible integration into different socio-cultural environments.

Modern practices of using cultural identity as a tool for branding, positioning, and differentiation of gastronomic projects are investigated. It has been established that effective strategies involve not just an appeal to ethnic stylistics but a deep work with cultural meanings, the involvement of traditionalists, the formation of an authentic brand narrative, and the use of the gastronomic space as a communicative platform. Interactive interaction models with the audience, digital means of popularizing cultural heritage, and localized strategies for cooperation with communities are particularly important. Such approaches contribute to the formation of emotional attachment of consumers, increasing trust in the brand, and creating a sustainable competitive advantage.

Prospects for further research lie in expanding the empirical base on the influence of cultural identity on consumer behavior in various regional and socio-cultural contexts, particularly through comparative case studies of gastronomic projects in multicultural urban spaces.

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